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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SUSTAINED
RELEASE FLOATING MATRIX TABLET FOR HERBAL
ANTI-MALARIALS****Bhati Deepak, Sable Kundan, Havelikar Ujwal, Ghuge Saurabh, Bhalekar Shriram**
ASPM'S K.T.Patil College of Pharmacy, Osmanabad, Maharashtra, India.**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Gastro-retentive system can remain in the gastric region for several hours and hence prolong. The gastric residence time of drug and improves the bioavailability. The aim of the work was to develop sustained release floating matrix tablet for hydro alcoholic extract of neem using psyllium husk as release controlling polymer drug and sodium carbonate as gas generating agent. The anti-malarial activity was due to hydro alcoholic extract of neem. The tablet was prepared by direct compression method. The formulated tablets were evaluated for different parameters like, thickness, Swelling index, friability, weight variation, hardness and in vitro drug release. It was observed that formulation containing combination of psyllium husk, and HPMC K -100 M, with NaHCO₃ as gas generating agents can be promising way for formulating gastro retentive drug delivery system.

Keywords: Gastroprotective floating Tablet, Antimalarials, Neem Extract, Evaluation and Formulation

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INTRODUCTION:

Malaria is a parasitic disease caused by the protozoa of the genus *Plasmodium*. It is a vector borne disease caused by bite of female anophylaxis mosquito carrying parasites. [1] There are four species of Plasmodium Parasites that can cause malaria infections in human which are *plasmodium falciform*, *plasmodium Vivax*, *plasmodium malaria*, *plasmodium ovale*. [2] *Azadirachata indica* is one of the promising medicinal plants, having a wide spectrum of well documented therapeutic activity. Neem has chemically diverse biologically active constituents with enormous therapeutic potential constituents like Nimbidin, Azadiractin and gedunin in neem tree are reported to possess antimalarial activity. Compounds of the alcoholic extracts of leaves and seeds are effective against both chloroquine resistant and sensitive strains. The antimalarial potency of neem can be explored that it's plasma concentration in the blood is maintained for a longer time and it's release from formulation is controlled. This can be achieved by designing a

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**A) Preparation of extract: [5]**

The leaves of *A.indica* were collected and shade dried on them pulverized in grinder. About 100gm powdered leaves utilised for extraction was passed through 120 mesh sieve to remove fine powder and course powder was used for extraction the powdered neem leaves were extracted with petroleum ether for removal of coloring matter by defatation process using continuous soxhlet extraction methods then the defatted neem leaves were refluxed with water and alcohol (1:1) for three hours to get hydroalcoholic extract the extraction temperature was maintained at 50°C the extract was filtered and concentrated to get thick paste and then powdered. All tablets were made by direct compression method. All ingredients were passed through seive no 80 on weight accurately. The extract, HPMC K 100M, sodium bicarbonate and psyllium husk were

floating drug delivery system for neem extract that will control. The rate of release for longer duration thus maintain plasma concentration.[3] The matrix polymer used in floating drug delivery system has bulk density lower than the gastric content. They remain buoyant in the stomach for a prolonged for continuous release of drug. Gastric emptying is much more rapid in the fasting state and floating system really heavily on the presence of foal to retard emptying and provide sufficient liquid for effective buoyancy. [4]

OBJECTIVE:

- 1) To study drug excipient interaction and preformulation parameter.
- 2) To prepare floating tablet from neem extract
- 3) Evaluation of herbal sustain release floating matrix tablet such as Disintegration, Dissolution, Hardness, Friability, In-vitro study.
- 4) To study stability of optimum formulation

mixed properly in a mortar and pestle to get a uniform tablet blend finally talc and magnesium stearate were mixed with the blend. The tablet blend was weight individually according to the formula and compressed into tablets using 10 stations tableting machine.

B) Formulation of tablet: [6]

All tablets were made by direct compression method. All ingredients were passed through sieve no 80 on weight accurately. The extract, HPMC K 100M, sodium bicarbonate and psyllium husk were mixed properly in a mortar and pestle to get a uniform tablet blend finally talc and magnesium stearate were mixed with the blend. The tablet blend was weight individually according to the formula and compressed into tablets using 10 stations tableting machine.

Table No.1: Formula of Tablet

Sr.no	Ingredient	Quantity	Uses
1	Neem	250 mg	Antimalarial
2	Psyllium Husk	95 mg	Matrix polymer
3	HPMC K 100M	65 mg	Matrix Polymer
4	Talc	20 mg	Glident
5	Magnesium Stearate	5 mg	Lubricant
6	Sodium bicarbonate	65 mg	Diluent
7	Acacia	0.11 gm	Thickening agent
8	Methyl paraben	0.01gm	Preservative

EVALUATION OF TABLET:**1) Preformulation study:****A) Angle of repose: [7]**

Angle of repose is used to check the flow ability of the granules in hopper before compression of tablet. Fixed funnel method is used to check the angle of repose. At the specific height the funnel was fixed on the graph paper which is placed horizontally at surface. Then the granules were passed to the funnel until the apex of the pile touched to the tip of the funnel. Radius was measured by using scale and determined the angle of repose by using following formula.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$$

Where,

θ - Angle of Repose
h - Height of pile.
r - Radius of pile.

B) Bulk Density: [8]

A known number of granules was transferred into a 25ml of measuring cylinder, carefully level the powder without compacting & measure the bulk volume

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \text{weight of powder} / \text{Bulk Volume}$$

C) Tapped Density: [9]

Tapped density is the ratio of weight of powder to the Tapped volume. It was determined by tapping a measuring cylinder containing fixed quantity of powder for the specific period of time. The tapped density was calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \text{Weight of Powder} / \text{Tapped volume.}$$

D) Hausner Ratio: [10]

It was determined after the measuring of Tapped density and bulk density. It is the densitification of the herbal powder mixture which may result from the vibration of the feed hopper which was calculated by using below formula

$$\text{Hausner Ratio} = \text{Tapped Density} / \text{Bulk Density}$$

E) Carr's Index: [8]

Carr's index was used to check the compressibility and flow of the granules from hopper. It is expressed

in percentage. Carr's index was calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Carr's Index} = \frac{\text{Bulk Volume} - \text{Tapped volume}}{\text{Bulk volume}} \times 100$$

2) Hardness: [11 - 12]

The Hardness of the Tablet is also called as Tablet Crushing strength. Hardness test is used to check the hardness of the prepared tablet. In this test we can measure the force which is required for the breaking of the tablet. Monsanto tablet hardness tester is used to check the hardness of the tablet. The hardness is expressed in Kg/cm².

3) Thickness: Thickness of all tablets was measured using the Vernier callipers.

4) Weight Variation: [13]

It is also called Uniformity of weight. In this evaluation test twenty tablets were weighed separately and then average weight was determined. The percentage deviation was calculated and checked for weight variation as per IP.

5) Friability Test: [14]

The friability test is used to check the combined effect of abrasion and shock. This test is used to check the tablet is suitable for transportation or not for that purpose Roche Friabilator is used it is laboratory friability tester. In that the preweighed antidiabetic tablet sample is placed in the friabilator which consists of plastic chamber that operates 100 revolutions for 4 min means 25 rpm. The tablet is then dusted and reweighed. Conventional compressed tablet that loses less than that 0.5-1.0 % of their weight are generally acceptable

6) In Vitro Drug Release Studies: [15]

Dissolution is the process by which a solid solute enters in the solution. It may be defined as the amount of drug substance that goes into solution per unit time. The disintegration test simply identifies the time required for the tablet to break up under the condition of test & all the particles are passed through mesh no.10 screen. The rate of drug absorption of acidic drug is high in GIT. So for that purpose the rate of dissolution is determined. For determination of dissolution rate of tablet we were taken 900ml of 0.1N HCL in basket of dissolution apparatus and which were rotated at 50 rpm and time limit of 20 min. A liquid of 5ml was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus at different time intervals and filtered. The accepted amount of dissolution limit for 20 min is not less than 80%.

Fig.1: Graphical Representation of drug release at specific time.

7) In Vitro Buoyancy Studies: [15-18]

The in-vitro buoyancy was determined by floating log time as per the method described by Rusa et al. The tables were placed in 250 ml beaker Contains 200 ml of 0.1 N HCL. The time required for tablet to rise the surface and floating log time (FLT) and the time period up to which the tablet remained buoyant is described as total floating time (TFT).

8) Swelling Study: [17]

The floating tablet were weighed individually (Designated as W_0) and placed separately in glass beaker containing 200 ml of 0.1 N HCL and incubated of 37°C. At regular 1hr time interval until 24hrs, the floating tablets were removed carefully using tissue paper. The swollen floating tablets were then reweighed (W_t) and % of swelling index was calculated using the following formula

$$\text{Swelling Index} = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100$$

RESULT:

Natural remedies are more acceptable as they are safer with fewer side effect than synthetic once, so a herbal antidiabetic tablet is nontoxic, safe, Efficacious and improve patient compliance as it contain herbal ingredient. This herbal antidiabetic tablet was evaluated for various evaluation test such as preformulation study (Angle of repose, bulk & Tapped density, Carr's index, Hausners ration), Hardness test, Weight variation test, Friability test and Dissolution test and they full fill the value.

1) Powder Blend:

Powder blend were evaluated for angle of repose, Bulk density, Tapped density, Hausner's Ratio, Carr's Index. The result showed that the precompressed blend has good flow property.

Table.2: Result of powder blend

Sr.NO	Evaluation parameter	Value
1	Angle of Repose	25.54°
2	Bulk Density	0.46 g/cm ²
3	Tapped Density	0.54 g/cm ²
4	Hausners Ratio	1.24
5	Carr's Index	14.37 %

2) Evaluation of Floating Tablet:

The floating tablet were evaluated for physical parameters such as hardness, Thickness, Weight Variation, % friability, Drug Content and swelling Index the result are shown in table no, All the parameters and its value were within permeable limits

Table.3: Result of evaluation of floating tablet

Sr,no	Evaluation Parameters	Observation
1	Total Weight	505.8 mg
2	Tablet Thickness	8.4 mm
3	% friability	0.52 %
4	% Drug Content	98.3%
5	Hardness	3.5 kg/cm ²
6	Swelling Index	243.2
7	Floating Lag Time	120 sec
8	Total Floating Time	13 hrs

CONCLUSION:

The effervescent based floating drug delivery system by employing matrix forming polymer (HPMC K/100 M, Psyllium Husk) and gel generating agent (Sodium Bicarbonate) was promising approach to increase the gastric residence time of hydro alcoholic extract of *Azadirachta indica* thereby improving its antimalarial efficacy.

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